

Severity Characteristics and Identification of Traffic Accident Prone Areas in Makassar City

¹*Hasmar Halim, Civil Engineering Department, Politeknik Negeri Ujung Pandang, Makassar, Indonesia.*

²*Ramlan Sultan, Civil Engineering Department, Politeknik Negeri Ujung Pandang, Makassar, Indonesia*

³*Zubair Saing, Associate Professor in Civil Engineering, Universitas Muhammadiyah Maluku Utara, Ternate, Indonesia.*

Abstract---High traffic accidents rate is one of the transportation problems in Makassar. Therefore, this study aims to determine the severity characteristics of traffic accidents and to identify accident prone locations in Makassar City using Upper Control Limit (UCL) method. The results showed that victims of male sex, double collision, motorcycle vehicle, driver, road accident and side-impact collision are the dominant variable affecting the severity of traffic accidents. Based on rationalization value of Equivalent Accident Number (EAN) that is weight for victim who suffered death by 10, serious injuries equal to 2,25, for minor injuries equal to 1,95 and 0,8 for having material loss. By using UCL method in Makassar City there are three road segments that are identified as accident-prone locations with the EAN value higher than UCL value. The three streets are *PerintisKemerdekaan, UripSumiharjo, and A.P. Pettarani..*

Keywords---Traffic accident, black site, equivalent accident number, upper control limit.

I. Introduction

With all the development and growth of transportation in an area in addition to providing benefits also have a negative impacts. Negative impacts can be congestion and queuing of course will cause great losses to road users, especially in terms of waste of time and low level of comfort [1]. One of the most highlighted issues is traffic safety that are almost certain every day there is an accident. Accidents that occur from minor to cause casualties due to various factors such as road, vehicle, or environmental and natural conditions.

In Indonesia, the increasing number of vehicles and human error is a major factor in increase traffic accidents. Police data show that in 2011 there were 109,776 accidents causing 31,185 deaths, while in 2012 there were 109,038 accidents causing 27,441 deaths, with potential socio-economic losses of IDR 203 to 217 trillion per year (2.9% 3.1% of Indonesia's GDP) or about 17.5 billion USD [2]. One way to reduce accidents is by knowing the accident-prone area so that appropriate mitigation can be found in the location [3].

Makassar City includes areas with high accident rates. Data from *Makassar Police Resort (Polrestabes)* noted that in 2015 recorded 810 events with a total of 1,223 people. From the data, it is known that the number of deaths caused by traffic accidents as many as 117 people, serious injured as many as 56 people, minor injuries as many as 917 people and who only experienced 133 material loss. It is quite alarming that the whole event is caused by human factors [4].

Identification, analysis, and improvement of roads in accident prone areas is one of the most effective approaches intraffic accidentsprevention [5]. For that reason, many studies related to accident-prone areas are conducted in two districts in Hanoi, Vietnam, concluding that the accident data is summarized and illustrated by the words in the Vietnam police ledger. This leads to difficulties in evaluating accidents but by using the symbol system in accident schemes, accident-causing analysis seems easier and more effective to do [6]. By using the technique of random accident location ranking analysis based on the value of Weighted Accident Number (WAN). The results obtained in the study concluded that in the National Road Lampung Province produced five accident prone areas [7]. Another study from the analysis of accident location (black spot) using EAN and UCL method in Kupang City revealed that on the East Road there are two locations identified as accident-prone areas [8].

Therefore, we need a study to obtain an accident characteristics related to accident identification of prone areas. In this study using Equivalent Accident Number (EAN) and Upper Control Limit (UCL) method as a guide in determining accident prone area on a road segment.

This article is devoted to the analyses of restorative justice paradigm, as well as the current practice of restorative justice programs in countries of Anglo-Saxon law, to identify positive experience and justify the proposals for the

consolidation of restorative justice programs in criminal procedure of the Russian Federation. In the results was made the conclusion about the necessity of legislative consolidation of the possibility of the use of restorative justice programs in criminal procedure of the Russian Federation.

II. Literature Review

One of the problems in big cities especially in developing countries is the high traffic accidents rate. Traffic accidents in addition to causing material losses also will further impact on human life activities. As a result of human activity accidents will be limited because of the serious injuries or minor injuries and even human activities will be stopped due to accidents because it causes death for the accident victims.

Accidents do not happen by chance, but there is a reason. Caused accidents should be analyzed and found, in order for corrective action is taken to prevent accidents. Traffic accidents can be defined as an unforeseen, unplanned, and unexpected that occurring on the highway or as a result of misconduct of a human activity on the road, which results in injury, illness, and harm to human beings or the environment

Another definition related to traffic accidents states that a traffic accident is a difficult event to guess where and when it happened. A person who experiences an accident will have physical and mental impact. Resulting in trauma, injury to disability and death. The rate of accidents increases from year to year as population growth and vehicle ownership. Heterogeneous traffic, poor traffic experience and poorer law enforcement further exacerbate the risk of accidents. The character and behavior of each individual also increases the risk of accidents [9].

Another definition reveals that a traffic accident is an unexpected and accidental road accident involving a moving vehicle with or without other road users, resulting in human casualties and loss of property [10, 11].

The severity of traffic accidents

Victims of traffic accidents are people who become victims of traffic accidents. In general, the severity caused by a traffic accident can be divided into 3 types: 1) dead (fatal), 2) serious injury, and 3) minor injury. Accidents that do not involve other road users are called single accidents. In addition, there are still types of traffic accidents without casualties, namely accidents with property loss only (property damage only = PDO accident). The impact of traffic accidents can be classified by casualties to four levels, [12]; a) Fatal Accident, is a victim of an accident that has been confirmed as a result of a traffic accident within 30 days after the accident; b) Serious Accidents are victims of accidents due to injuries suffering from permanent disabilities or having to be admitted to hospital within a period of more than 30 days from the time of an accident. An event is classified as a permanent defect if a member of the body is lost or cannot be used at all and cannot recover forever; c) Minor Accidents are casualties injured who do not require hospitalization or have to be hospitalized from 30 days; and d) Material Loss, accidents that only cause material loss.

Equivalent Accident Number (EAN)

The crash equivalent number is the number used for the accident class weighting, this number is based on accident value with damage or material loss. The Equivalent Accident Number (EAN) is a numerical economic scale for weighing accident rates. This is calculated by comparing the estimated economic losses caused by various accident rates, ie the death toll (M), serious injury or severe injury (B), minor injury (R), or damaged property only (K). The technique of identifying crash ratings is done by determining the accident weight. There are several types or degrees of accidents based on the victim severity so that the accident number can be synchronized with the accident number being the accident weight. The value of weighting depends on method used. In Indonesia, the following methods are used; 1) Using the crash equivalent number with a weighting system, which refers to an accident cost [13]: M: B: R: K = 12: 3: 3: 1; 2) Accident Point Weightage (APW) Method. This method divides the severity with four major categories with each having the following weights [14]: M: B: R: K = 6: 3: 0.8: 0.2; 3) The accident equivalent number can be calculated by summing the incidence of accidents on each kilometer of road length then multiplied by the weight value according to the severity. The standard weights used are [15]: M: B: R: K = 12: 6: 3: 1; 4) The crash equivalent number used by the Indonesia Police: M: B: R: K = 10: 5: 1: 1. Thus there are some EAN values suggested for determining accident-prone areas. This EAN value uses a rationalized average value as shown in Table 1.

Upper Control Limit (UCL)

As outlined in the handling of accident-prone locations, the determination of accident-prone locations using statistics with the Upper Control Limit (UCL) method, is shown in equation 1.

$$UCL = \lambda + \psi x \sqrt{\left(\frac{\lambda}{m} + \frac{0,829}{m} + \left(\frac{1}{2} x m\right)\right)} \quad (1)$$

Where is:

λ = Average accident rate in accident unit per exposure

ψ = probability factor = 2.576

m = unit exposure, km

Road segment with accident value (EAN) above UCL is defined as accident-prone location. Possible Factor value (ψ) is determined by probability, in which the accident rate is large enough that this accident occurs cannot be considered a random event. Possible factor (ψ) as shown in Table 2. The most commonly used value of ψ is 2,576 with probability 0.005 (or 99.5% significance) and 1,645 with probability 0.05 (or 95% significance) [16].

Table 1:Equivalent accident number

The Severity	Methods				The average value of rationalization
	research and development center	APW	Indonesia Police	Land Transportati on	
Death (M)	12	6	10	12	10
Major (B)	3	3	5	6	4,25
Minor (R)	3	0,8	1	3	1,95
Material Loss (K)	1	0,2	1	1	0,8

Table 2: Probability factor value

Probability	0,005	0,0075	0,05	0,075	0,10
ψ	2,576	1,960	1,645	1,440	1,282

Accident Prone Areas (Black Site)

The accident-prone areas are the areas with the highest accident rates, the highest accident risk and the highest accident potential on a road. These accident-prone areas can be identified on specific road locations (black spots) as well as on certain roads (black site). General criteria used to determine black spot and black site [17]:

1. Black spot

The number of accidents over a certain period exceeds a certain value, the accident rate (per-vehicle) for a certain period exceeds a certain value, the accident number, and the accident rate, both exceeds a certain value, and the accident rate exceeds the critical value.

2. Black site

The number of accidents exceeds a certain value, the accident number per km exceeds a certain value, and the accident rate or the accident number per vehicle exceeds a certain value.

Common criteria that can be used to define black spots are; a) have a high accident rate; b) locations of accidents are relatively piled up; c) accidents occur in a relatively same space and span of time; d) have the cause of accident with a specific factor.

III. Research Methodology

The location of the study was conducted in Makassar City on all identified roads that had occurred traffic accidents. The traffic accident data obtained from Traffic Accident Makassar Police Resort Unit. The data collected is the accident data for 2012-2015 periods. The data is then compiled and analyzed to illustrate the accident in Makassar City. Description of accident will be known the accident characteristics, victim severity, and accident-prone locations.

*Corresponding Author: Zubair Saing, Email : zubairsaing.umm@gmail.com

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In conducting an analysis to obtain accident-prone areas (Black Site), accident data are classified by road. The method used is Equivalent Accident Number (EAN) and Upper Control Limit (UCL). The road segment identified as accident-prone is when the EAN value is greater than the UCL value. The identification and priority of the crash site black location is done using the following methods; 1) creating a tabulation between road segment and victim severity who had an accident on the road; 2) determining a road segment with 15 or at least 10 crash sites based on highest accident frequency from 3 years accident data in a row; 3) calculate the total number of accident weight (EAN); 4) calculate the average EAN of entire road segment; 5) conduct a road rank based on accident weight; 6) determine the UCL value; 7) determine accident prone locations by comparing UCL value with EAN. If the EAN value is greater than UCL it can be categorized as accident prone area.

IV. Results And Discussions

Traffic Accidents Identification

As one of the cities in Indonesia which has a high growth rate of vehicles, it gives impact to increasing accident number in Makassar city. In general, the data collected from the Police Traffic Accident Unit of Makassar City as an accident management authority in Makassar City provides an overview of the accident within 2012 - 2015 as shown in Table 3.

In Table 3, shows that accidents in Makassar City have a tendency to decrease accident number. Likewise with casualties number resulting from the accident. However, in general the risk of accidents in Makassar City is high enough to reach 2.5 accidents per day and casualties reached 1.5 people/accident. While the level of losses caused from an accident reached IDR 2,208,189/accident. Based on Table 3 it is also known that there is a tendency for accident to occur in the same place with the proportion reaching 5 locations per accident.

Table3:Traffic accident identified in Makassar City in 2012 – 2015

Indicators	Years				Average
	2012	2013	2014	2015	
Number of Accidents	1,051	961	781	810	901
The number of victims	1,581	1,494	1,192	1,222	1,372
Died	139	133	114	115	125
Serious Injuries	293	257	228	56	209
Minor injuries	977	927	716	918	885
Material Loss (IDR)	1,639,240,000	2,212,215,000	2,062,065,000	1,887,930,000	1,950,362,500
Number of location points	200	207	180	170	189

Severity Characteristics of Traffic Accidents

Victims of traffic accidents in Makassar City in 2012-2015 on average reaches 1,372 people annually, consists of 77.4% occurred in male-sex at the victim severity who died. The average of overall men casualty reached 73.8% in all severity of traffic accidents. Whereas based on the location, accidents occurring on average roads may result in 75.07% of all traffic accidents severity and the rest occur at the intersection and turn areas. In addition, accidents that occur on the road can cause deaths of 77.8% compared with serious injuries and minor injuries, as shown in Fig. 1 (a) and (b).

In the accident type category, double accidents or accidents involving two vehicles is a type of accident that has a considerable risk. The average percentage of accidents reached 68.57% at all severity levels. The highest score on each accident type is 34.5% for single accident type will cause death. While for the double type accidents of 74.4% will cause minor injuries. Likewise, in a successive accident will cause minor injuries of 5.9%. For vehicles category involved in accidents, a motorcycle is vehicle type that has the highest risk can cause death, serious injury and minor injuries. Overall averages 78.73% for all severity levels and the rest for non-motorized vehicles and cars / buses / trucks. More as illustrated in Fig. 1 (c) and (d).

The victim's position as driver has the highest percentage in all categories of severity. That is 68.7% of drivers experiencing accidents will cause death compared to pedestrians and passengers is only 15.7% or 4.4 times greater. While the position of the victim as a passenger has the second highest risk after the driver. Overall the average passenger has an accident risk of 18.03% of all accident rates. In Makassar generally, accidents resulting from a rear end collision, head-on collision, hit and run, hit site and sideswape. Of all collisionstypes, the road side has the highest risk that will cause death, serious injury and minor injuries, average of 49.63%. While the smallest risk occurs in collision type from the front with an average of 5.83% as shown in Fig. 1 (e) and (f).

Accident-Prone Areas Identification

For the identification of accident-prone areas the data used are traffic accidents in 2012-2015 obtained from the traffic accident unit of Makassar Police Resort Unit. The data collected is accidents number and severity of the period. The next basic analysis is road segment identified as the worst accident site. The location of intended accident is a road with 15 or at least 10 crash sites based on highest accident frequency of accident data 3 years in a row [13]. Therefore, the 15 road segments that have the highest frequency as shown in Table 4.

Fig.1: Percentage of accidents based on severity

Table 4: The frequency and number of traffic accident victims in 2012-2015

Street Name	Death	Serious Injury	Minor Injury	Property Damage Only	Frekwensi
P. Kemerdekaan	66	128	554	72	533
Urip Sumorharjo	33	61	279	36	263
Ap. Pettarani	21	49	239	48	232
Veteran	23	27	128	15	124
St. Alauddin	14	16	102	22	108
Metro Tj. Bunga	21	24	86	11	93
Ir. Sutami	38	22	60	10	92
Cendrawasih	6	23	97	7	76
Jend. Sudirman	5	15	71	8	64

*Corresponding Author: Zubair Saing, Email : zubairsaing.umm@gmail.com

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Ratulangi	6	13	52	10	54
Jalan Tol	9	7	43	30	53
Bandang	12	6	43	15	52
Abd. Daeng Sirua	3	15	56	10	51
G. Bawakaraeng	8	15	55	7	51
Hertasning	5	7	42	14	47

In determining the accident-prone areas (black site) there are several methods that can be used, among others, is by using Equivalent Accident Number (EAN) method. This method considers the weight of each severity. This weight is to determine the limits of road defects against accidents on each road segment. Each road has different limits depending on accident number and the casualty severity. In this study the weight of each severity level uses the average value of the four weighted accidents used in Indonesia. As described in Table 1, the category of victims who experienced death has a weight of 10, serious injuries of 4.25, minor injuries of 1.95 and material loss of 0.8.

The equivalent accident number (EAN) is the sum of overall severity. For example, on *Perintis Kemerdekaan* Street the number of victims who died as many as 66, for serious injuries as many as 128, minor injuries as much as 554 and loss of material as much 72. Thus, the equivalent accident value is 2,341.90. After calculation of total EAN value is obtained, then calculated to get the average accident value. The average accidents value is 565.98. The total value of crash equivalent and upper control limit for fifteen road segments in Makassar as shown in Table 5 below.

Table 5: Weight of equivalent accident number and upper control limit

Street Name	EAN				Total EAN	UCL
	D	SI	MI	PDO		
P. Kemerdekaan	660	544	1.080	57.6	2,341.90	654.13
Urip Sumorharjo	330	259	544	28.8	1,162.10	628.10
A.P. Pettarani	210	208	466	38.4	922.70	621.34
Veteran	230	114	249	12.0	606.35	610.90
St. Alauddin	140	68	198	17.6	424.50	603.62
Metro Tj. Bunga	210	102	167	8.8	488.50	606.33
Ir. Sutami	380	93	117	8.0	598.50	610.61
Cendrawasih	60	97	189	5.6	352.50	600.33
Jend. Sudirman	50	63	138	6.4	258.60	595.52
Ratulangi	60	55	101	8.0	224.65	593.58
Jalan Tol	90	29	83	24.0	227.60	593.76
Bandang	120	25	83	12.0	241.35	594.55
Abd. Daeng Sirua	30	63	109	8.0	210.95	592.77
G. Bawakaraeng	80	63	107	5.6	256.60	595.41
Hertasning	50	29	81	11.2	172.85	590.37
Sum	2,700	1,819	3,718.7	252,0	8,489.7	

From the result of accident data analysis from 2012-2015, therefore determined the accident-prone area (black site) by using Upper Control Limit (UCL) method. The results show that there are three streets having Equivalent Accident Number (EAN) greater than UCL value. These three road segments are classified as accident-prone areas (black sites). The description of the three streets in Makassar City that are classified as accident-prone areas, as follows; a) Perintis Kemerdekaan street has an EAN value of 2,341.90 greater than UCL value of 654.13; b) Urip Sumiharjo Street has an EAN value of 1,162.10 greater than UCL value of 628.10; c) AP Pettarani Street has an EAN value of 922.70 greater than the UCL value of 610.90. Graphically the black site identification as seen on Fig. 2.

V. Conclusions

Makassar city is one of the cities with a high accident rate. Recorded during 2012-2015 periods of 3,603 with the number of casualties reached 5,489 and loss of material reached IDR 7,801,450,000. In general, shows that the gender of men who have an accident has a higher severity tendency than women. The proportion reaches greater than 70%. The same thing happens to roads, double accidents and motorcycles have a tendency to generate high risk severity. While the victim position as a driver has a larger average of 60% at all severity levels. For the collision

type highest risk occurs from the side with a greater percentage of 40%. The accident-prone areas in Makassar City identified three road segments that fall into that category. PerintisKemerdekaan Street, the accident equivalent number generated 2,341.90 with UCL value of 654.13. While on UripSumiharjoStreet has UCL value of 628.10 and EAN value of 1,162.10. For AP Pettarani Street has an EAN value of 922.70 more with a UCL value of 610.90.

Fig. 2: Identification of Black Site with UCL method

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